

Deep Learning Based Histological Classification of Inflammatory Bowel Disease Samples Derived From Non-Linear Multimodal Imaging

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Abstract

This study presents a deep learning-based approach for classifying inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) using non-linear multimodal imaging data. Conventional histopathological diagnosis relies on labor-intensive H&E staining and manual interpretation, which limits scalability. By integrating Coherent Anti-Stokes Raman Scattering (CARS), Second Harmonic Generation (SHG), and Two-Photon Excited Fluorescence (TPEF), we captured rich, label-free tissue information from biopsy samples. Deep learning models—including CNN, VGG16, Inception V3, and ResNet50—were trained on image patches with and without augmentation. Evaluation through two cross-validation schemes revealed that augmented data significantly boosted classification performance, with ResNet50 achieving over 95% patient-level accuracy. Compared to traditional machine learning approaches that rely on handcrafted features and expert annotations, deep learning offered superior accuracy and scalability. To interpret model decisions and enhance transparency, Grad-CAM activation maps were generated, providing spatial localization of relevant features. Additionally, explainable AI (XAI) methods were employed to gain deeper insights into model behavior and feature relevance. Our findings demonstrate the potential of combining multimodal imaging with deep learning and XAI to automate, enhance, and better understand histological diagnosis of IBD.

Keywords: IBD, Deep Learning, Multimodal Imaging, XAI.

1 Introduction

Inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD), including Crohn’s disease and ulcerative colitis, are chronic conditions that require accurate diagnosis for effective treatment. Conventional diagnosis relies on H&E-stained histopathology and manual assessment by experts—a process that is time-consuming, subjective, and difficult to scale.

Non-linear multimodal imaging presents a promising, label-free alternative by capturing biochemical and structural features in a single scan. Techniques such as Coherent Anti-Stokes Raman Scattering (CARS), Second Harmonic Generation (SHG), and Two-Photon Excited Fluorescence (TPEF) provide complementary insights into tissue lipid content, collagen structure, and metabolic activity, respectively—without the need for dyes.

However, interpreting such high-dimensional data remains a challenge. Traditional machine learning methods depend on handcrafted features and manual annotations, which may be biased and insufficient to capture the complexity of multimodal data.

To overcome these limitations, we apply deep learning (DL) models for automated feature extraction and classification of IBD tissue. Using convolutional neural networks (CNN, VGG16, Inception V3, ResNet50), we train on multimodal image patches from 20 patients, employing data augmentation and two cross-validation schemes (leave-1-patient-out and 5-fold CV). We also explore model interpretability through Grad-CAM visualizations and explainable AI (XAI) techniques to better understand decision-making.

Our approach demonstrates that deep learning not only improves scalability and accuracy but also offers interpretability on par with, or superior to, traditional ML pipelines—paving the way for clinically viable, automated histological analysis.

Figure 1 : Overview of the workflow

2 Methods

This study utilized a multimodal imaging and deep learning pipeline to classify colon biopsy samples from patients with and without inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Tissue sections were imaged using three complementary label-free modalities: Coherent Anti-Stokes Raman Scattering (CARS), Second Harmonic Generation (SHG), and Two-Photon Excited Fluorescence (TPEF). CARS, tuned to 2930 cm^{-1} , visualized lipid content via CH_2/CH_3 vibrational modes; SHG (415 nm) highlighted collagen and myosin fiber structures; and TPEF (415 nm) captured intrinsic fluorescence linked to metabolic activity. These modalities provided rich, multi-dimensional representations of tissue morphology and biochemistry without the need for stains or dyes.

Figure 2: Origin of multimodal images and the relevant content captured by each modality

Data were collected from 20 patients—13 healthy and 7 diseased. Whole-slide images (WSIs) from each modality were segmented into non-overlapping patches of 224×224 pixels, yielding approximately 800 patches. To improve the training dataset and mitigate class imbalance, patches were augmented using brightness and contrast adjustments, Gaussian noise, and horizontal flipping, resulting in a total of ~ 2400 image patches. The patch distribution reflected the underlying class ratio (2:1, healthy to diseased).

For classification, we employed four convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures: a baseline 2D-CNN (10M parameters), VGG16 (14.7M), Inception V3 (21.8M), and ResNet50 (23.5M). These models were trained to distinguish between healthy and diseased tissue at the patch level, and patient-level predictions were computed using majority voting over the corresponding patches. Model evaluation was conducted using two cross-validation schemes: (1) leave-1-patient-out (LOPO), where each patient served as a test case in turn, and (2) 5-fold cross-validation, with 4 patients held out in each fold. This ensured patient-level data separation and robust generalization testing.

Training was performed from scratch on the augmented dataset, with early stopping based on validation accuracy. To interpret model decisions, we employed Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM), which generated heatmaps identifying spatial regions in the input image most influential to the final prediction as shown in the Figs 3 and 4.

3 Results

Deep learning models were evaluated using leave-1-patient-out (LOPO) and 5-fold cross-validation at both patch and patient levels. Across all models, data augmentation consistently improved classification performance.

In the LOPO scheme, ResNet50, Inception V3, and VGG16 achieved over 95% patient-level accuracy. The 2D-CNN showed the greatest improvement—from 55% to 100%—with augmentation. Patch-level results also remained strong, though slightly lower due to within-sample variability.

The 5-fold scheme, involving higher inter-patient variability, resulted in slightly lower accuracies. ResNet50 maintained top performance with 91% patch-level accuracy when augmented, followed by Inception V3 and VGG16. The 2D-CNN remained the least effective. These findings highlight the advantage of deeper models in handling complex multimodal data.

Augmentation methods—brightness, contrast, noise, and flipping—enhanced model generalization, especially for simpler architectures. Grad-CAM visualizations, shown in Figure 4, confirmed that models focused on biologically relevant features such as glands, inflammatory zones, and fibrotic tissue, particularly in SHG and CARS channels.

Overall, ResNet50 emerged as the most robust architecture. Combined with augmentation and patient-wise validation, the deep learning models achieved strong, interpretable diagnostic performance, supporting their potential clinical utility. Despite the promising performance, several limitations should be acknowledged. While the dataset size (20 patients) is relatively limited, it serves as representative proof of concept demonstrating the feasibility of combining multimodal imaging and deep learning for IBD classification. Although the study does not extensively elaborate on clinical integration, the proposed label-free workflow has the potential to significantly reduce diagnostic turnaround time by eliminating the need for staining and enabling automated analysis. Furthermore, the imaging modalities employed are compatible with *in vivo* implementations in the future, offering a path toward real-time, non-invasive diagnostics. Further studies with larger cohorts and clinical workflow alignment will be necessary to evaluate scalability, cost-efficiency, and integration into routine practice.

Figure 3 GRAD-CAM heatmap of the last CNN layer for a disease (top) and healthy (bottom) sample

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